

REVEALING EXPLORATION OF FACTORS ASSOCIATED WITH CONTRACEPTIVE PRACTICES AMONGST ELIGIBLE COUPLES OF ANGANWADI IN URBAN SLUM OF DISTRICT BHOPAL - A CROSS SECTIONAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Family planning is crucial for population to attain good health and quality life. Contraceptive use not only decreases unintended pregnancies and reduces infant and maternal mortality and morbidity but also helps in national reforms. This study sought to determine the coverage and determinants of contraceptive's usage among eligible couples of a slum in Bhopal district.

Methods: This cross-sectional community based study was conducted from March 2022 to May 2022. Out of 375, about 200 eligible couples were selected by stratified random sampling method from slum area of Damkheda Anganwadi, field practice area of L N Medical College, Bhopal.

Data was collected from a semi structured proforma. It contains questions regarding sociodemographic characteristics and contraceptive practices of participants. Percentage and proportion used for statistical analysis along with Chi Square test.

Result: Majority of women participants belonged to 25- 34 years of age, all were married and hindu and out of them 53% belonged to schedule caste and 52% were from lower middle socioeconomic status. The couple protection rate observed 72%. One third of participants used barrier method as contraception. Use of contraception and socioeconomic status were found significantly associated (p value = 0.04).

Conclusion: Couple Protection Rate was found appropriate in study population, though different factors age of women, literacy status of female partner, socioeconomic status, type of family and

number of living children affect contraceptive behavior. Study highlights the need for Information Education Communication activity and constant interaction by health workers with the eligible couples for boosting family planning program and availability of contraception to their door step.

Keywords: Contraception, Couple protection rate, Eligible couple, Family planning practices, Bhopal.

Introduction: After decades of knowing that China bore the title of being the most populous country in the world, things are about to change. India, who had the title of second highest populations has taken over the top spot citing a ‘population explosion’. A couple of years ago Prime Minister Narendra Modi had pointed out India’s “population explosion”, expressing concern. He also lavished praise on families who carefully considered the impact of more babies — on themselves, and the nation. However, data has shown that despite the population explosion, India's population growth pace has reduced (according to UN data).

The Family Planning Division's goals, tactics, and initiatives are created and implemented with the intention of accomplishing the family welfare objectives and goals outlined in a number of policy documents (NPP: National Population Policy 2000, NHP: National Health Policy 2002, and NRHM: National Rural Health Mission) as well as to uphold the government of India's promises (participating in the FP-2020 summit, the MDG: Sustainable Development Goals, the ICPD: International Conference on Population and Development, and others).

Between 1971 and 1981, India’s population was growing on average 2.2% each year. By 2001 to 2011, that had slowed to 1.5% and is even lower now. According to UN projections, India’s population is expected peak at about 1.7 billion in 2064. “When the fertility rate drops, the population continues to grow for several decades. And that is because younger, large cohorts are still growing into that age when they become parents,” told by Frank Swiaczny, senior researcher at the Federal Institute for Population Research. Therefore, India’s population will continue to grow slowly because of the considerable number of women entering their reproductive years.¹

A species must reproduce in order to survive, yet such startling increase would undoubtedly result in a shortage of many essentials. In India, family planning began with this idea. India implemented the First Five Year Plan, a population policy in 1952 as the first nation to attempt to manage the population expansion. However, the plan was ultimately unsuccessful.

The government later developed more potent strategies to rein in the population boom by the 1970s. The Medical Termination of Pregnancy Act (1971), birth control slogans on bills and posters, the minimum age for marriage, contraception, etc. were among them.

Early marriage, low death rate, illiteracy, birth rates, poverty, unemployment, religious superstitions, standard of living, better health facilities, illegal migration, lack of reproductive education & absence of family planning leading to population explosion in India.

India was the first country in the world to have launched a National Program for Family Planning in 1952. Family planning is crucial for population to attain good health and quality life in the current scenario of “Population explosion”. As a mode of control & prevention, contraceptive use not only decreases unintended pregnancies and achieve population stabilization goals but also promote reproductive health and reduce maternal, infant & child mortality and morbidity. Couple Protection Rate is an indicator of the prevalence of contraceptive practice in the community. Its definition is - the percentage of eligible couples effectively protected against childbirth by one or the other approved methods of family planning like

- Sterilization
- IUD
- Condom
- OCP's

Net Reproductive Rate = 1 can be achieved only if the CPR > 60%.

Family planning has undergone a paradigm shift and emerged as one of the interventions to reduce maternal and infant mortalities and morbidities. It is well-established that the states with high contraceptive prevalence rate have lower maternal and infant mortalities. Greater investments in family planning can thus help mitigate the impact of high population growth by helping women achieve the desired family size and avoid unintended and mistimed pregnancies. Further, contraceptive use can prevent recourse to induced abortion and eliminate most of these deaths.

In order to get a rough estimate, this study sought to determine the coverage and determinants of contraceptive's usage among eligible couples of a slum of Bhopal district.

Objectives

- To determine the extent of contraceptive use in study population,
- To study association of contraceptive use with various socio– demographic factors.

Methodology

Study Design - Cross sectional community based study.

Study Period - March 2022 to May 2022 (3 months)

Study Subjects - All eligible couples of slum area Damkheda Anganwadi No. 5 who have given written consent to participate in the study were included in the study.

* An Anganwadi is a government sponsored child care & mother care centre in India.

* Eligible Couples Definition: A currently married couple wherein the wife is in the reproductive age (i.e. 15 -49 yr. of age)

Sampling Method - Stratified random sampling method

Tool And Technique - Pre design, pretested, semi structured questionnaire for interview. It contains questions regarding sociodemographic characteristics and contraceptive practices of participants.

Data Collection - Appointment with the participant was taken and those agreed were asked to sign the consent form. Interview done using the questionnaire.

Sample Size – These slums cater a total population of 1,127.

- Sample size was estimated taking contraceptive prevalence of 67% with allowable error 10% at 95% confidence interval.
- Non respondents were considered 10%. • Accordingly, estimated sample size was 180.
- The study was conducted among 190 eligible couples, residents of Damkheda slums of Bhopal.

Analysis Statistical Plan –

Statistical analysis was done using excel spread sheets. Analysis was done in the form of percentages, proportions and represented in tables.

- Final data was analyzed quantitatively in terms of frequency/number and percentages & Chi Square test was used to analyse association.

Results

Majority of women participants belonged to 25- 34 years of age. All were married and Hindu by religion and out of them 53% belonged to schedule caste and 52% were from lower middle socioeconomic status.

The couple protection rate observed was 72%. One third of participants used barrier method as contraception. The use of contraception and socioeconomic status was found significantly associated (p value = 0.04). All the required data in this regard is compiled in Table No. 1.

Awareness wise about 33.68% were known to condom method, 32.63% were aware about LTT (tubal ligation), only 6.31% were aware about NSVT (vasectomy) & 27.37% were unaware about any of the available sterilization method.

Table No. 1: Distribution of Study Participants as per Number (N) & Percentages (%) for various sociodemographic characteristics and contraceptive practices.

Characteristics	Yes	No	Chi – Square Value	P Value
	N (%)	N (%)		
Age (years)				
15-24	10 (50)	10 (50)		

25-34	72 (81.82)	16 (18.18)	4.83	0.09
>34	56 (68.29)	26 (31.71)		
Religion				
Hindu				
Caste				
General	10 (62.5)	6 (37.5)	3.88	0.14
OBC	52 (81.25)	12 (18.75)		
SC	74 (72.55)	28 (27.45)		
ST	2 (25)	6 (75)		
Education				
Illiterate	50 (64.10)	28 (35.90)	4.31	0.12
Primary	30 (93.75)	2 (6.25)		
Middle	34 (77.27)	10 (22.73)		
High	16 (66.67)	8 (33.33)		
Higher	4 (50)	4 (50)		
Graduate	4 (100)	0 (0)		
Socioeconomic status				
II	18 (81.82)	4 (18.18)		
III	38 (65.52)	20 (34.48)		
IV	90 (90)	10 (10)		
V	6 (60)	4 (40)		
Type of Family				
Nuclear	124 (70.45)	52 (29.55)		
Joint	14 (100)	0 (0)		
Number of living children				
0	24 (92.31)	2 (7.69)		
1	24 (85.71)	4 (14.29)		
2	70 (92.11)	6 (7.89)		
3+	42 (70)	18 (30)		

Discussion: Globally, family planning laws range greatly from one another, reflecting disparities in social norms, cultural standards, and economic conditions. An examination of these policies in comparison can yield important information about how well they work and how they affect population growth and reproductive health.

Family planning policies in many developed countries, like those in Western Europe and North America, often prioritise granting access to a variety of contraceptive alternatives, offering thorough sexual education, and defending the reproductive rights of women. These nations

typically have lower fertility rates, which demonstrates how well these policies have worked to give people the freedom to choose how they want to procreate.

However, in order to slow down the rate of population growth, certain developing nations that are already overpopulated, such as Bangladesh and India, have put in place explicit population control measures. These strategies include instituting sterilization programs, providing incentives for fewer families, and encouraging the use of contraception. Sterilization became popular in India in the 1970s as a result of financing from the UN Population Fund, the World Bank, and the Swedish International Development Authority, which pushed powerful individuals to sterilize impoverished men. Although these measures have somewhat reduced fertility rates, they have also sparked worries about coercion and the infringement of human and reproductive rights.

In our study, we tried to explore about basic socio demographic profile of some eligible couples in a slum area & tried to reveal about their awareness status & user friendliness related to available common contraceptive methods.

In a similar study of Rizvi A et al. it was discovered that although 46.7 percent of married women used contraceptives, 99.2 percent of them were aware of them. The most popular form of birth control was the condom. Approximately 56.3% of women who had previously taken contraceptives were now using them. Reliability to health risks or side effects was the primary cause of stopping contraceptive use.

Makade KG et al. revealed that 87.7% of women knew how to use at least one form of birth control. At the time of the survey, 68.4% of women were using a contraceptive. 14% of the ladies did not know that there was a nearby medical centre that offered contraception. There was virtually little emergency contraceptive knowledge and use.

Kumar A research work in 2011 in Lucknow showed that the more literate women became, the more accepted family planning techniques—both temporary and permanent—were. 53.40 percent of them utilised IUCD, 38.83% OTC tablets, and just 7.77 percent of their partners used condom. 33.4% have had mini-lap sterilisation and 66.6% have had laparoscopic surgery. Nobody had a vasectomy, not even one partner. Higher educated people accepted the permanent technique after one or two children, whereas illiterate and primary school graduates accepted it after three or more children. A total of 70.27% of those who accepted permanent techniques reported having side effects, compared to 23.30% of those who used temporary methods.

In a 2014 study conducted in Raipur, Bandhi G found that, of 711 women, 91.56% were aware of one or more methods of contraception, and 53.2 percent had either used or were currently using it at the time of the survey. Of them, permanent procedures were utilised by 49.23%, and temporary ways by 3.8%. In the current survey, the percentage of non-users was 32.9%. Anaemia, weakness, lactational amenorrhoea (47.01), fear of adverse effects (29.49%), and husband's compulsion to not use them (13.67%) are the main excuses for not using them.

In West Bengal, Gupta A et al. found that young adults (20–29 years old) made up the bulk of their study group (59%) and that 65% of them came from nuclear households. One-third of the participants had married before turning 18 years old. 67.50% of CPR users employed permanent techniques. Significantly more couples who used contraceptives were married between the ages of 18 and 24 (75%), came from a nuclear family (70%), were literate up to class 10 (73%), had three or more live children (77.50%), and were from a class II socioeconomic background (80%). The percentage of literate women above the national norm, with 92.50% of eligible couples' wives possessing literacy, while the most prevalent method of contraception was tubectomy.

Nisha Ram Relwani of Nagpur (2015) found that younger women had more unmet needs; as a result, family planning programmes should concentrate on this age group and target urban slum regions and uneducated individuals. Family planning should place a strong emphasis on counselling and communication with women, as well as dispelling common misconceptions concerning contraceptives.

When used properly, family planning is an essential tactic to lessen the adverse effects of population growth. By providing people, particularly those in poor nations, with the information and resources necessary to manage their fertility, we can foster happier, more stable families, robust economies, and sustainable development.

Family planning is not a stand-alone remedy, though; combating overpopulation calls for a multipronged strategy that also includes advancing ecological practices, gender equality, and better education.

In the end, a global family planning effort can guide us towards a sustainable future characterised by social justice and resource equity.

The environment and many facets of society would be impacted by this decline in reproduction rates. One benefit would be an improvement in sustainability since it would lessen the demand on resources like food, water, and energy. By lowering rates of maternal and infant mortality and extending the life expectancy and general health of women, it may also enhance public health outcomes.

These outcomes are not assured, though. Overcoming obstacles like political resistance, financial constraints, and cultural hurdles is critical to the success of family planning initiatives. Furthermore, ageing populations and migration patterns can have a big impact on future population trends, even in the case of successful family planning programmes.⁸

Conclusion

Couple Protection Rate was found appropriate in our study population, though different factors age of women, literacy status of female partner, socioeconomic status, type of family and number of living children affect contraceptive behavior.

Recommendations

There are appx. 150 – 180 eligible couples per 1000 population in India. These couples are in need of family planning services. The “eligible couple register” is maintained and updated by the ANM/MPHW/ASHA. Study highlights the need for Information Education Communication activity and constant interaction by health workers (ANM/MPHW/ASHA) with the eligible couple for boosting family planning program and availability of contraception to their door step. Cafeteria Approach & Community Need Assessment Surveys ought to do the right thing.

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